

TYPES OF MARKET STRATEGIES OF THE CONSTRUCTION COMPANY

**U.A. Mukhammadiyev is an associate professor of Samarkand State
University of Architecture and Construction**

Abstract: This article is devoted to the creation of a market strategy for a construction company, in which the company's strategy formulation, marketing strategy, price formation strategies, and market coverage strategies are analyzed according to their importance.

Keywords: enterprises, strategic management, market economy, operational management, marketing, management.

In the conditions of developed market relations, creation of a market strategy that corresponds to it and its implementation is one of the most important functions of the company's top management level.

A strategy is a general program of operations that identifies the critical issues for the firm and the resources it will need to achieve its primary goals.

The market strategy of the construction company is the formation of goals, their implementation for each type of goods and specific markets, and solving related tasks. Taking into account the capabilities of the construction organization and the market situation, its strategy is created to realize production and commercial goals. This strategy clearly shows how to use the marketing system, how to attract consumers in the target markets and how to realize the goals set for the organization. In this case, the main task of the marketing system is to plan marketing, introduce the product to the market and ensure its movement in the market, sell it and set the price.

The following four steps are used in the formation of the market strategy of

the construction organization.

- goals of the construction organization;
- the goals of the marketing department;
- the construction organization's order portfolio formation and development plan;
- knowing exactly which of the basic strategies (mainly growth strategy) to use in the development of the construction organization.

The composition of the construction organization's business portfolio consists of a set of goods and services offered for sale in target markets. In this case, the business portfolio of the construction organization can be formed according to the goods and services intended for the main consumers or groups of consumers of the goods. It depends on the market policy of the construction organization and the importance of the consumer group for the construction organization. Effective implementation of these functions in a construction organization belongs to the marketing department. But if the various loads related to defining the goals and performing the specified tasks in the marketing department increase, then it is possible to establish a "business strategies department". This section helps the construction organization to create certain goods and services and offer them to target markets or certain segments of it.

The goods and services that a construction organization creates can be categorized into Stars, Cash Cows, Problem Kids, and Dogs using a model developed by the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) in the 1970s. The BCG matrix of the construction company's business portfolio represents the company's situation, taking into account the growth rate of a specific industry and the relative market share. Relative market share is determined by the ratio of the market share of a particular enterprise to the market share of the largest competitor in the respective industries.

It is important to correctly choose one of the main strategies for the growth

of enterprises. Any organization must continuously plan for future growth and development. First of all, access to new and promising markets creates opportunities for sustainable development of the organization. However, services and goods offered to new markets should meet consumer demand and satisfy their needs. There are other ways of sustainable development of the organization. They can be expressed mainly in three different directions of construction organization development.

- intensive development of construction organization;
- integrated development of construction organization;
- use of similar and non-similar diversification strategies.

The organization's market strategy is created on the basis of knowing the patterns of changes in target markets, analyzing them, adapting to changes in customer behavior, being aware of competitors' market strategies, and other such important information. Common market strategies are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Existing product product	Existing product product	
Existing market	Access to the market (A ₁)	Product creation (A ₂)
New market	Market development (A ₃)	Diversification (A ₄)

Ansoff matrix

The organization's market strategy and behavior, its behavior is determined by the competitiveness of its goods in the market, scientific and technical development and patent level of the resource base.

Market entry strategy (A₁) is a natural strategy for most companies trying

to expand market share in target markets. The market development strategy (A_2) assumes that the construction organization adapts to living conditions and introduces existing goods to new markets. This strategy means that it can be applied only to the competitive goods and services that the enterprise produces. In relation to non-competitive goods, the strategy of creating new goods (A_3) or the strategy of diversification (A_4) can be used. Қурилиш корхонасининг маркетинг стратегиясини қуйидаги турларини ўзида мужассам этади:

- A market segment analysis strategy for effective sales of a product consists of the following:
 - monosegment market of goods sales;
 - the dominant segmental market of the sale of goods;
 - a semi-segmented market for the sale of goods;
 - change the market structure of the sale of goods.
- Market Expansion Strategies:
 - expansion of the coverage of the market where goods are sold;
 - reduction of market segments;
 - maintaining existing market segments.
- Strategies for competing in commodity markets:
 - focus (power) on attracting the consumer;
 - focus on product advertising;
 - focus on competitors and competitive strategy;
 - strategies for forming commodity prices;

The formation of prices at the cost level includes the following:

- individual costs for a specific product;
- expenses at the level of production costs.

The formation of prices based on the level of customer demand for goods reflects the following:

- leadership on low prices of goods and prices in general;

- formation of prices based on the principle of "chasing the captain";
- cost recovery pricing.

It is important to solve communication problems and tasks in the implementation of market strategies. Communication strategies and employee incentives are created by the planning officer and the representative of the construction organization for the implementation of this project.

- It is these specialists who develop the planned provision of the product, the market, sales channels, the level of profit, and the costs of product advertising. After that, the plan of the advertising campaign is drawn up.
- The market coverage strategy is based on one of the following three strategies or a combination of them.
- undifferentiated marketing, in which the construction organization does not take into account the existing differences in market segments, offers the same type of goods to all consumers in all markets.
- differentiated marketing - in which the needs of the consumers in the target markets are studied, and the goods are offered that exactly match their behavior and demand.
- concentrated marketing - in which pressure is applied to the target market segment by the organizers of the marketing complex (product, price, methods of distribution and sale of the product, and incentives).

When choosing a market coverage strategy, the following factors should be taken into account: the resources of the construction organization (if resources are limited, the appropriate strategy for the situation is the concentration marketing strategy), the presence of goods in the same type (it is recommended to use an undifferentiated strategy for one type of goods), the life cycle of the product stages (when entering the market with a new product, it is appropriate to use an undifferentiated or concentrated marketing strategy), the level of a single

category of the market (it is necessary to use an undifferentiated marketing strategy to customers with homogeneous needs), marketing strategies of competitors (if competitors use segmentation of target markets, in such a situation, undifferentiated marketing use can be disastrous for the organization, on the other hand, if competitors are using undifferentiated marketing strategy, the organization can use differentiated and concentrated marketing strategy and achieve positive results).

Market coverage strategies are divided into five areas:

- concentration in the single market segment;
- focusing on the same consumer demand (same product group);
- focus on one group of consumers;
- selective specialization in several market segments (focusing on several groups of consumers with several types of goods);
- full coverage of the market (all goods will be directed to all groups of buyers).

Usually, most companies start choosing target market segments from one segment, and if this step is successful, they try to occupy other segments. The order of market segment capture is carefully analyzed as part of a comprehensive plan. For example, Japanese firms start by capturing market segments that their competitors have neglected. At the same time, they gain reputation due to quality satisfaction of consumer needs. Only then will they introduce their activities to other market segments. Japanese firms using this marketing strategy have been successful in the global market segments such as automobiles, cameras, watches, home electronics, steel supplies, marine vessels, and others.

Therefore, successful business strategies are based on competitiveness that provides market advantage. There are several sources of competitiveness: offering the best quality goods and services to the customer market, reducing costs compared to competitors, effective use of marketing services, use of similar and

non-similar diversification, use of a market strategy suitable for the organization, and others.

REFERENCES

1. Буриев, Х. Т., and И. А. Усманов. "Принципы совершенствования системы управления региональным строительным комплексом." *Большая Евразия: развитие, безопасность, сотрудничество* 6-2 (2023): 310-312.
2. Буриев, Х. Т., and И. А. Усманов. "Принципы совершенствования системы управления региональным строительным комплексом." *Большая Евразия: развитие, безопасность, сотрудничество* 6-2 (2023): 310-312.
3. Усманов И.А., Буриев Х.Т. Совершенствование механизмов стимулирования повышения качества в сельском строительстве // Collection of scientific articles. 2017. №3. С. 53-54.
4. Буриев Х.Т., Усманов И.А. Пути совершенствования стимулирования повышения качества работ в сельском строительстве // Часопис економічних реформ. 2017. №4(28). С. 25-30.
5. Nuriddinovna, Mukumova Nargis, and Saydirasulov Alisher Zokirovich. "The Main Stages in the Development of the Digital Economy of Uzbekistan." *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 2.6 (2023): 178-182.
6. Shavkatovna, Komilova Mukammal, and Shernazarov Temurbek Tulkinovich. "IMPROVEMENT OF ACTIVITIES OF HOUSING AND UTILITIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN." *World Bulletin of Management and Law* 22 (2023): 25-27.
7. Usmanov, I. A., and Sh N. Jumanov. "WAYS TO IMPROVE ACCESS CONTROL IN CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT." *Science and innovation* 1 (2022): 384-386.

8. Usmanov, Ilhom Achilovich, and Jumanov, Sherzod Norboevich. "WAYS TO IMPROVE QUALITY CONTROL OF CONSTRUCTION AND INSTALLATION WORKS" *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, vol. 1, no. 10, 2021, pp. 651-658.
9. Usmanov, I. A., and Sh N. Jumanov. "WAYS TO IMPROVE ACCESS CONTROL IN CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT." *Science and innovation* 1 (2022): 384-386.
10. Буриев, Хаким Тошимович, and Ильхом Ачилович Усманов. "A development strategy for the construction industry in Uzbekistan: organizational aspects of implementation." *Недвижимость: экономика, управление* 4 (2021): 70-74.
11. Мухаммадиев, У. А., and З. А. Мирзаев. "ПУТИ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН." *ББК 31.15 я431+ 38я431+ 65.441 я431 Э653*: 139.
12. Мухаммадиев, У. А., А. Б. Мирзаев, and З. А. Мирзаев. "СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИИ МАГИСТРАЛЬНЫХ ТРУБОПРОВОДОВ." *Социально-экономическое развитие городов и регионов: градостроительство, развитие бизнеса, жизнеобеспечение города*. 2018.
13. Рузиева, Комила Эрназаровна, and Баходир Темурович Мухаммадиев. "СОЗДАНИЕ НОВОЙ ПЦР (ПОЛМЕРАЗНЫЕ ЦЕПНЫЕ РЕАКЦИИ) СИСТЕМЫ (REAL-TIME) ДЛЯ ОБНАРУЖЕНИЯ LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES В ПИЩЕВЫХ ПРОДУКТАХ И В ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЕ." *Universum: технические науки* 10-4 (103) (2022): 19-23.
14. Мухаммадиев, У. А., Ш. Н. Жуманов, and З. А. Мирзаев. "В СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВЕ КРУПНЫХ КОМПЛЕКСОВ СВОЕВРЕМЕННОЕ

- ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЕ ФРОНТОВ РАБОТ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРОИЗВОДИТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТРУДА." *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research* 2.6 (2022): 1238-1240.
15. Shavkatovna, Komilova Mukammal, and Abdixoliqov Jamshid Abdixalilovich. "THE ROLE OF EMPLOYEES IN ENSURING THE LABOR POTENTIAL OF ENTERPRISES." *IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* 2.12 (2022): 135-137.
16. Musakulovna, Rakhmonova Feruza, Komilova Mukammal Shavkatovna, and Shernazarov Temurbek Tulkinovich. "USE OF MARKETING CONCEPTS IN THE ACTIVITY OF ORGANIZATIONS IN THE CONDITIONS OF FORMING AN INNOVATIVE ECONOMY." *World Economics and Finance Bulletin* 17 (2022): 55-56.
17. Shavkatovna, Komilova Mukammal, and Olimova Lola Erkinovna. "WAYS OF EFFICIENT USE OF LABOR RESOURCES IN THE COUNTRY." *World Economics and Finance Bulletin* 7 (2022): 85-90.
18. Komilova, M. S., & Abdikholikov, J. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF EMPLOYEES IN ENSURING THE LABOR POTENTIAL OF ENTERPRISES. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(11), 481-484.
20. Buriyev X.T., Komilova M.Sh. *Qurilishda menejment // Darslik. Toshkent. 2022. 276.*
21. Жуманов, Ш. Н., М. Ш. Комилова, and А. Х. Ташимов. "МАРКЕТИНГ" ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШДАГИ ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВА ИЛФОР ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ." *Экономика и социум* 4-1 (107) (2023): 586-589.
22. N.I. Asoff. *Corporate Strategy – Penguin Books. Middlesex. 1981*
23. Артур А. Томпсон – м.и А. Дж. Стрикленд III. М 2002г.
24. У. А. Мухаммадиев. *Стратегик менежмент. Тошкент. 2021йил*

25. Мухаммадиев, У. А., А. Н. Жабриев, and А. Б. Бектемиров.
"Стратегик менежмент." *Ўқув қўлланма. Тошкент* (2010).